

ATOPIC DERMATITIS IN CHILDREN

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Annotation. The problem of atopic dermatitis in children takes on special significance in contemporary medicine. Within structure of allergic diseases in children atopic dermatitis possesses one of the leading places by its prevalence. Yet, many issues of this problem remain still unsolved. The present paper reviews references of home and foreign authors who generalize contemporary notion of the classification, approaches to treatment and prevention of atopic dermatitis. Key words: atopic dermatitis, children, diagnostic criteria, local and general therapy. The problem of allergic skin lesions in children is currently one of the most pressing in the practice of a pediatrician.

Among allergic skin diseases in children, one of the leading places is atopic dermatitis, the prevalence of which, according to epidemiological studies, ranges from 17 to 25% [6]. A large number of epidemiological studies indicate a higher frequency of allergic diseases in cities compared to rural areas, as well as in economically developed countries compared to countries with developing economies. The high prevalence of atopic dermatitis in the child population, the continued growth of its severe forms, the tendency to chronicity, and insufficiently studied medical, biological, and socio-hygienic development factors determine the relevance of this problem. Atopic dermatitis occurs in all countries, in both sexes, in different age groups. To date, the prevalence of AD in the US pediatric population has reached 17.2%, in children in Europe - 15.6%, in Japan - 24%, which reflects a steady increase in the incidence of AD over the past three decades.

The frequency of AD is significantly higher in residents of economically developed countries, the incidence of AD increases significantly in migrants from disadvantaged areas. The prevalence of AD symptoms in various regions of the Russian Federation (RF), according to the results of a standardized epidemiological study within the ISAAC (International Study of Asthma and Allergy in Childhood) program, amounted to 6.2 to 15.5%. Clinical guidelines suggest an increase in this indicator by 1.9 times in the pediatric population of the Russian Federation. In recent years, the Expert Committee on Asthma and Allergy of the World Health Organization

Regional Office for Europe has developed the Global Allergy and Asthma European Network (GA2LEN) program. The GA2LEN study on the prevalence of allergic diseases among 15-18-year-old patients has allowed the accumulation of the most reliable data on the problem in Russian adolescents. A one-time parallel group study was conducted in Moscow and Tomsk in a continuous sample of children aged 15 to 18 years. According to the study, the presence of disease symptoms was detected in 33.35% of adolescents, the prevalence of atopic dermatitis, according to the questionnaires, was 9.9%, the diagnosis was verified in 6.9% of study participants. Among respondents with current AD, the proportion of girls was 1.6 times higher than that of males ($p = 0.039$). The results of the observation show significant discrepancies with the official statistics on AD in the child population (in 2008, the official incidence of AD in Moscow was 1.3% - 5 times less than the study showed).

The purpose of this publication is to review and systematize the literature data devoted to the development of modern concepts of atopic dermatitis in childhood. Atopic dermatitis is a chronic allergic disease that develops in individuals with a genetic predisposition to atopy, has a relapsing course with age-related features of clinical manifestations and is characterized by exudative and (or) lichenoid rashes, an increase in the level of serum IgE and hypersensitivity to specific and non-specific irritants.

In the development of atopic dermatitis in children, endogenous and exogenous risk factors should be distinguished:

I. Endogenous: heredity; atopy; skin hyperreactivity.

II. Exogenous: triggers: non-allergenic (psychoemotional stress, weather changes, tobacco smoke, food additives, pollutants, xenobiotics); allergens (food, household, epidermal, fungal, bacterial, vaccinal); aggravating factors for triggers: climat poor nutrition; poor skin care, vaccination; significance. Sensitization to food allergens is facilitated by the anatomical and physiological characteristics of the child's body: functional immaturity of the digestive organs, well-developed vascularization of the mucous membrane of the gastrointestinal tract, lack of local immunity - all this contributes to the penetration of undigested macromolecules into the child's bloodstream.

The recognition of the allergic (immunological) concept of the development of atopic dermatitis served as a reason for a comprehensive study of its immune mechanisms, especially IgE-mediated reactions. A study of the concentrations of total and specific IgE antibodies in children with atopic dermatitis showed that in 85.5% of them, the levels of total IgE significantly exceeded the indicators of healthy children. Thus, in the pathogenesis of atopic dermatitis, an important place belongs to immunological mechanisms, changes in regulation at the cytokine level, which determines the specificity of the mechanisms of development of this disease and in connection with which studies aimed at clarifying the extent of these disorders and searching for methods of drug correction of the observed changes are of particular relevance. Currently, there is no official generally accepted classification of atopic dermatitis. Based on many years of clinical observations, study of the etiology and available morphological data, V.A. Revyakina, I.I. Balabolkin, L.S. Namazova et al. (1998) developed a working classification of atopic dermatitis in children [1].

Results of the study. The initial stage of the disease is reversible provided that treatment is started in a timely manner with appropriate elimination measures and appointment of a hypoallergenic diet. It is at this stage of the disease that it is easiest to reverse the development of skin rashes. Untimely and inadequate treatment of skin manifestations leads to the transition of the initial stage of the disease to the stage of pronounced pathological changes in the skin with typical morphological elements. Clinical manifestations of atopic dermatitis at this stage are quite diverse, which is reflected in a more detailed (compared to the above) classification [3]. The exudative form is characterized by facial hyperemia, edema, exudation (weeping), and crust formation. Later, rashes may appear on the skin of the outer surface of the shins, forearms, torso, buttocks. Red or mixed dermographism is characteristic. Itching of the skin of varying intensity is noted.

This form is more common in children in the first year of life. The erythematous-squamous form is characterized by hyperemia and slight swelling of the skin, the appearance of itchy nodules, small vesicles, erosions, peeling and scratches. Exudation is not typical for this form. The erythematous-squamous form Health and Ecology Problems of atopic dermatitis is more often detected in children aged 2-3 to 10-12 years. The erythematous-squamous form with lichenification is manifested by erythematous-squamous foci with the presence of small flat and follicular papules. The skin is lichenified, with a large number of scratches and small-plate scales. Skin rashes occur mainly on the flexor surface of the limbs, the anterior and lateral surface of the neck, and the back of the hands. Characteristic is white persistent or mixed dermographism. This form of atopic dermatitis is typical for children from 2 to 12 years old.

The lichenoid form of atopic dermatitis is more often observed in adolescents and is characterized by dryness and an emphasized pattern of the skin, edema and infiltration. Large merging foci of lichenification of the skin are found against the background of erythema. Various clinical manifestations of atopic dermatitis can be combined in different combinations and vary in each specific case, in connection with which it is advisable to distinguish three main clinical and morphological forms of this disease: exudative, proliferative and mixed.

All clinical manifestations of atopic dermatitis occurring with exudation phenomena are attributed to the exudative form, and skin manifestations with foci of infiltration and lichenification - to the proliferative form. The simultaneous presence of foci of exudation, infiltration, lichenification in patients is considered a mixed form of atopic dermatitis.

Based on the history of the disease, the characteristics of the clinical course and the results of an allergological examination, etiological variants of atopic dermatitis associated with food, mite, fungal allergies, with household, pollen, polyvalent sensitization are distinguished. The prevalence of the skin process is assessed by the location of the lesions on the skin. If skin rashes are noted on the face, trunk, limbs and (or) in the area of the folds of large and medium joints, then atopic dermatitis is assessed as widespread. If the skin process is limited only to the area of the face and neck or the folds of large and medium joints or is localized around the wrists or shins, then this is localized atopic dermatitis. When assessing the severity of atopic dermatitis,

the severity of inflammatory manifestations on the skin, the intensity of itching, enlargement of the lymph nodes, the frequency of exacerbations and the duration of remission are taken into account. Mild atopic dermatitis is characterized by small skin rashes in the form of mild hyperemia, exudation, mild peeling, isolated papulovesicular elements, mild itching of the skin, and enlarged lymph nodes up to 3–4 mm. The frequency of exacerbations is 1–2 times a year. The duration of remission is 6–8 months. In moderate to severe cases, there are multiple lesions on the skin with fairly pronounced exudation, infiltration, lichenification, excoriations, and crusts. Itching is moderate or severe. The lymph nodes are enlarged to 5–8 mm. The frequency of exacerbations is 3–4 times a year.

The duration of remission is 2–3 months. Severe atopic dermatitis is characterized by multiple and extensive lesions with pronounced exudation, persistent infiltration and lichenification, with deep linear cracks and erosions. Itching is severe and constant. Frequency of exacerbations is more than 5 times a year. Duration of remission is 1–1.5 months. In most cases, children with atopic dermatitis have concomitant manifestations: cutaneous (dry skin, periorbital shadows, palmar hyperliarity) and extracutaneous (allergic conjunctivitis, allergic rhinitis, bronchial asthma). In patients with atopic dermatitis, concomitant pathology is quite often detected: diseases of the gastrointestinal tract (80–97%), nervous system (55–60%), pathology of ENT organs (50–60%), diseases of the respiratory system (30–40%), urinary system (20–30%), protozoan-parasitic invasion (18–20%).

The prognosis of atopic dermatitis depends on the presence of atopy in relatives, the characteristics of the course of pregnancy and childbirth, the time of the first manifestations of the disease, concomitant pathology, the patient's mental state, and the adequacy of therapy. The diagnosis of atopic dermatitis in typical cases does not present significant difficulties. Due to the lack of pathognomonic tests and criteria for atopic dermatitis, this diagnosis in most cases is made based on the main and additional diagnostic criteria proposed by J.M. Hanifin, G. Rajka, K.D. Cooper in 1986 [8, 9]. The main diagnostic criteria for atopic dermatitis include: itching of the skin, typical morphology and location of the rash, a tendency to chronic relapsing course, personal and family history of atopic disease, white dermographism. Additional diagnostic criteria for atopic dermatitis include: xerosis, ichthyosis, hyperlinear palms, cheilitis, angular cheilitis, Keratosis pilaris, Pityriasis alba, pale skin, periorbital shadows. A variety of diagnostic criteria (three main and three additional) is sufficient to diagnose atopic dermatitis. However, some domestic and foreign scientists believe that the diagnosis, especially in the early stages and with a latent course, should be made on the basis of minimal signs and confirmed by modern laboratory diagnostic methods, the most important of which include specific allergological examination, immune status study, stool analysis for dysbacteriosis. Most patients with atopic dermatitis are sensitized to a wide range of allergens. Skin tests allow you to identify the suspected allergen and take preventive measures.

However, the involvement of the skin in the pathological process does not always allow this examination to be carried out. The concentration of serum IgE is elevated in more than 80% of patients with atopic dermatitis and is often higher than in patients with respiratory diseases. The degree of increase in total IgE correlates with

the severity of the skin disease. It should be noted that 20% of patients with typical manifestations of atopic dermatitis have a normal IgE level. Thus, the determination of total IgE in the blood serum helps in diagnosis, but it cannot be fully relied on when making a diagnosis, prognosis and management of patients with atopic dermatitis.

In addition, in recent years, RAST, MAST, and ELISA methods have been widely used to determine the content of specific IgE antibodies in vitro [5]. Modern therapy of atopic dermatitis is pathogenetic and is aimed at eliminating pathological disorders in organs and systems, as well as preventing exacerbations of the disease. It includes elimination measures, drug therapy, local therapy and rehabilitation measures. Therapy should be strictly individual, taking into account the clinical form, stage and period of the disease, concomitant pathological conditions and complications [7]. Among the elimination measures, the leading place is occupied by the exclusion of causative food allergens with the appointment of specialized diets, the effectiveness of which depends on the completeness of the detection and exclusion of all allergenic products from the diet. In this case, an indispensable condition is their replacement with food products equivalent in nutritional value and calorie content. Specialized diets have not only therapeutic, but also diagnostic and preventive capabilities. It is advisable to record reactions to food based on an analysis of the food diary before prescribing an elimination diet to a child. At the beginning of the child's examination, before receiving the results of specific diagnostics, a diet is used from which suspected food allergens, obligate allergens (milk, eggs, fish, coffee, cocoa, chocolate, honey, nuts, vegetables and fruits containing red, yellow pigments, etc.), as well as products capable of causing non-specific histamine release (cheese, sauerkraut, legumes, spinach, etc.) are excluded.

Since cow's milk proteins are the causative allergen in the development of allergies in young children, the main principle of diet therapy is to exclude milk formulas and replace them with formulas based on soy protein isolate. However, a large number of children with cow's milk protein intolerance also develop intolerance to soy proteins.

Hypoallergenic formulas based on milk protein hydrolysates with a small degree of hydrolysis have been recently developed for the nutrition of such patients. They are used for mild food allergies, as well as when it is necessary to transfer children with a burdened allergy history to artificial feeding. In such formulas, the fat and carbohydrate components are similar to those in conventional adapted formulas; the amino acid set of the protein component is close to the composition of breast milk. These formulas are complete and balanced, enriched with vitamins, microelements, and taurine. Along with the elimination diet, patients with atopic dermatitis are prescribed drug therapy: drugs that have an antihistamine and antiserotonin effect, agents that inhibit the release of biologically active substances from mast cells, drugs that normalize the functional state of the gastrointestinal tract, sorbents, sedatives and immunomodulators. Of the antihistamines, preference should be given to second-generation drugs (claritin, hismanal, treksil, zirtek, kestine, etc.), which selectively act on peripheral H1 receptors, have less neurotoxicity and sedative effect and are increasingly used in the treatment of atopic dermatitis. These drugs help to relieve acute manifestations of allergies.

With long-term use of second-generation antihistamines (up to 2-3 months), a decrease in exacerbation episodes is noted and clinical remission is achieved. In the treatment of atopic dermatitis, drugs are used whose action is aimed at inhibiting the secretion of allergy mediators (zaditen, ketotifen, nalcrom). These drugs are used for prophylactic treatment in a long course (at least 2-3 months). Drugs that normalize the function of the digestive organs are prescribed to improve the breakdown of allergic food substances and correct enzymatic disorders. For this purpose, abomin, festal, digestal, panzinorm, creon, hilak-forte are used. The duration of the course of treatment should not exceed 2-3 weeks. According to a number of authors, in the acute phase of the disease, it is advisable to prescribe enterosorbents: carbolene, activated carbon, polyphapan, bilignin, etc. (in a short course of up to 5-7 days). With atopic dermatitis, as a rule, the intestinal biocenosis is disrupted. Eubiotics are used to eliminate it.

Depending on the severity of neurovegetative disorders, it is necessary to use sedative therapy that has a regulating effect on the central nervous system (valerian extract, motherwort tincture, peony). In some cases, it is necessary to resort to prescribing tranquilizers (rudotel, diazepam, meprobamate). The course of atopic dermatitis can be aggravated by hypovitaminosis A. Therefore, it is advisable to prescribe an oil solution of vitamin A in an age-related dosage (1000 IU per 1 year of the child's life). In young children, in order to avoid overdose, it is preferable to use an aqueous solution of vitamin A. In atopic dermatitis occurring with signs of immune deficiency, immunomodulatory agents can be effective. It is believed that the use of thymalin, taktivin, and vilosen helps reduce allergy symptoms and lower the level of total Ig E in the blood serum. Local therapy in children with atopic dermatitis is carried out differentially, taking into account the condition of the skin and is aimed at eliminating and resolving inflammatory changes that have developed on the skin. Local treatment includes ointments, creams, solutions, and lotions. Lead water, copper sulfate solution, potassium permanganate solution, and freshly brewed black tea solution have an astringent effect.

1% methylene blue solution, Castellani liquid, fucorcin dry the skin and have an antimicrobial effect. 1% menthol solution, 20% aqueous glycerin solution, and zinc-containing chatterboxes have a drying and antipruritic effect. 5% salicylic ointment, Unna cream, zinc-naphthalan ointment, birch tar, ichthyol help eliminate infiltration and lichenification. In recent years, topical glucocorticosteroids have occupied an important place in the treatment of atopic dermatitis. Most of them have side effects, the risk of which depends on the patient's age.

Among modern non-fluorinated corticosteroid drugs for external use, advantan deserves special attention. It has pronounced biological activity and a high degree of safety. The drug has various dosage forms (emulsion, cream, ointment, fatty ointment) and can be used in young children (starting from 1-2 months). The emulsion is recommended for use in exacerbation of skin inflammation, oozing skin, and lesions of the skin of the face and scalp.

The cream is advisable to prescribe for acute and subacute processes on the skin, including on the face and skin folds. The ointment should be used for subacute and chronic dermatitis. Fat ointment is effective in the chronic course of the disease with increased dryness of the skin. Advantan is a diester with high lipophilicity, which

allows it to quickly and deeply penetrate the stratum corneum of the skin and enter the bloodstream, quickly inactivating itself. Active connection with skin receptors provides its prolonged effect and makes it possible to use the drug 1 time per day. The course of treatment, as a rule, does not exceed 14 days. Physiotherapy is an important stage in the system of staged therapy of atopic dermatitis. In complex treatment, physiotherapeutic procedures with a local and systemic effect are used: alternating magnetic field, ultrasound treatment, electrosleep, polarized light, laser therapy, acupuncture. These factors are used strictly individually, taking into account the form and period of the disease, the severity of the disease and the presence of concomitant diseases. Prevention of atopic dermatitis should be carried out even before the birth of the child. Pregnant women and nursing mothers are prescribed a hypoallergenic diet, especially those who suffer from allergic diseases. Children from the risk group for the development of allergic diseases are recommended to breastfeed for as long as possible.

Conclusion. A review of the literature data allows us to conclude that the problem of atopic dermatitis in children is relevant and requires further research in order to develop diagnostic criteria for the disease and more effective treatment methods. Patients of the pediatric age category with AtD should be under constant dispensary supervision of a pediatrician, consultations with specialists (allergist-immunologist, dermatologist) depending on the condition and severity of the process are carried out once every 2-6 months. A comprehensive examination with dynamic monitoring of the condition, determination of changes in the spectrum and degree of sensitization, as well as rehabilitation programs are carried out for children depending on the severity and nature of the course of the process according to indications on an outpatient basis or in a day hospital. In case of severe atopic dermatitis and or slowness to therapy, after clarification of the diagnosis, treatment in a 24-hour/day hospital is indicated.

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